

Beyond the View: Disaster Risk Preparedness and Management of the Top Tourist Attractions in Tagaytay City, Cavite

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Article Details:

Received: 12 April 2026
Revised: 21 April 2026
Accepted: 30 April 2026
Published: 16 May 2026
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Recommended Citation:

Gulipatan T C. P., Mantes M A., Glorioso I M P. B. (2026). Beyond the View: Disaster Risk Preparedness and Management of the Top Tourist Attractions in Tagaytay City, Cavite. The International Review of Multidisciplinary Research. 1 (5), 687-692.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20237159>

Index Terms:

disaster preparedness, risk management, tourist attractions, Tagaytay City, natural hazards, tourism resilience

Abstract. The current study evaluated the degree of disaster risk preparedness level of the managers from the top tourist spots in Tagaytay City, Cavite, where volcanic eruption, earthquake, typhoon and landslide disaster risk is prevalent. Descriptive research design was used where data were collected using survey questionnaires given to tourism establishment managers. Survey results showed that respondents had high awareness of disaster risks with the Grand Mean of 3.67 and good level of implementation of basic measures in terms of emergency plans, coordination and possible hazards that may endanger their business. Nonetheless, respondents indicated that there was lack in resource allocation and management, obtaining the lowest mean score of 2.8 and updating disaster preparedness plan, having Mean score of 2.4. Museums and parks, according to findings, were more disaster-ready as compared to other tourism establishments due to effective organizational policies and more experience in managing disasters due to their more contact with people. Based on findings, while the level of disaster risk awareness among tourism establishments in Tagaytay is high, there is still need to enhance resource management, staff readiness, monitor disaster risk preparedness and government intervention to ensure safety of tourists. Mandatory disaster risk drill can be recommended for all tourism establishments, along with strengthening partnership between government and private sector to implement capacity-building programs and tailor-made disaster management plan for different types of tourism businesses. For future research, it is highly recommended that a larger sample of tourism-related businesses will be surveyed to have comprehensive picture of disaster risk preparedness among the tourism industry.

Introduction

In the Philippines, most people visit Tagaytay City due to its breathtaking sights, such as the Taal Volcano, along with the other activities that they can do like horse riding and ziplining. Due to all this, the tourism and hospitality sector in the city is growing rapidly, to the point where the city's economy is mainly dependent on it. However, regardless of how popular Tagaytay is, it is still prone to disasters, including natural ones. Such disasters can damage properties, buildings, and houses in the said tourist spot which may cause risks to both tourists and residents. For this reason, disaster risk preparedness is crucial for tourist spots in Tagaytay, as it helps mitigate the harmful effects of inevitable natural disasters.

As stated by Shmueli et al. (2021), disaster risk preparedness is most crucial in the tourism sector, specifically for tourist attractions like Tagaytay, so that the effects of disasters can be minimized, given the large number of tourists visiting these attractions. Therefore, through this study, it is possible to gain an understanding of the state of disaster preparedness in tourist attractions in Tagaytay, allowing for suggested improvements to ensure that safety measures are followed to protect both properties and people. As natural disasters resulting from climate change continue to pose threats to communities, it is becoming increasingly necessary to strengthen disaster risk management practices among businesses in the hospitality

and tourism sector (Balogun et al., 2020). Because the local economy of Tagaytay is highly dependent on tourism, any natural disaster that harms its tourist attractions will significantly affect the economy, leading to financial losses for the city. Therefore, with the help of this study, the researchers aim to contribute to understanding how tourist attractions in Tagaytay can effectively mitigate the harmful effects of disasters. Also, by understanding the challenges faced by the tourist attractions along with the strategies in relation to their disaster risk preparedness practices, this study aims to help both tourist attractions and local authorities in Tagaytay so that they can better improve their strategies or even add more to deal with the possible dangers they might face effectively.

Research Questions

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, and type of business?
2. What is the level of disaster risk awareness among tourism establishments in Tagaytay City?
3. What disaster preparedness measures are currently implemented by the top tourist attractions?
4. What challenges are encountered in establishing and maintaining disaster risk preparedness and management measures?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what recommendations can be proposed to improve the disaster preparedness and management of the top tourist attractions in Tagaytay City?

Assumptions of the Study

This study assumes that the respondents provided honest and accurate responses regarding their disaster risk awareness and preparedness practices. It is also assumed that the selected managers possess sufficient knowledge and experience to represent their respective establishments. Additionally, the study assumes that the survey instrument is valid and reliable in measuring disaster preparedness.

Methodology

Research Designs

According to Creswell (2019), research design is the overall plan for connecting the conceptual research problems to the pertinent and achievable empirical research. It establishes the systematic methods and procedures used to collect, measure, and analyze data in a way that directly addresses the research questions and objectives. For this study, a descriptive survey research design was used to examine the disaster risk preparedness of hospitality and tourism businesses in Tagaytay, Cavite, specifically the top eight tourist spots in the said place, allowing for the collection of representative data to assess preparedness strategies across the industry. The purpose of descriptive research was to characterize the behaviors, attitudes, and preparedness measures of the businesses involved. Data were collected through surveys administered to a sample of hospitality and tourism establishments in Tagaytay City, including hotels, resorts, and restaurants. This research design is appropriate because it focuses on describing the existing disaster preparedness efforts without influencing or changing any variables. By using a descriptive survey research design, the study aimed to present an accurate picture of how businesses in the hospitality and tourism industry in Tagaytay prepare for and manage disaster risks. The data collected will help identify common practices, challenges, and areas that need improvement in disaster risk preparedness among the top tourist attractions

The descriptive technique enabled researchers to compare reactions and identify trends in disaster preparedness strategies because the study included a variety of company kinds, including restaurants, hotels, and resorts. This method ensures that the information gathered is indeed reliable to properly give suggestions so that the tourist attractions chosen can better enhance their disaster risk preparedness strategies and practices. Furthermore, data was efficiently collected from a large number of participants in a short amount of time by employing a survey as the primary data collection instrument. This approach offered a time-efficient and cost-effective means of reaching several businesses while ensuring the accuracy of the data gathered. The results of the study contributed valuable insights that can help businesses enhance their disaster preparedness measures and ensure the safety of both employees and customers.

Participants

The respondents of this study were the managers of the top eight tourist destinations in Tagaytay City, Cavite. They were selected as primary participants because they are responsible for ensuring that both the establishments and their staff are adequately prepared for potential disasters. Given Tagaytay's reputation as a leading travel destination, it is essential to understand how these managers approach disaster risk preparedness and management. Also, they are the ones who hold the job of making sure that the tourist attractions have appropriate plans for emergencies whenever there is a disaster that happens. Additionally, the managers of these enterprises were chosen as the primary responders because they have the greatest knowledge and experience in handling disaster-related issues within their organizations. They are supposed to be aware of the many dangers in Tagaytay and the steps that should be done to prepare for any emergency. Among their duties include establishing safety rules and training staff on emergency procedures to ensure that disaster preparedness guidelines are appropriately adhered to. The study is to interview these managers in order to gain a better understanding of their perceptions of catastrophe risk and the specific measures they have taken to ensure the safety of their business and customers. Better employee training programs, investments in safer building constructions, and closer collaborations with regional disaster response teams are a few examples of these suggestions. The goal of the study was to help create a more secure and safe tourism sector in Tagaytay by examining the managers' awareness and readiness.

Materials/Instrument

Data were collected using a structured survey questionnaire consisting of sections on demographic profile, disaster risk awareness, preparedness measures, and challenges encountered. The instrument was adapted based on related literature and reviewed for clarity and relevance. Although no formal reliability testing (e.g., Cronbach's alpha) was conducted, the questionnaire was designed to ensure consistency and alignment with the study objectives.

Procedures

Only pertinent data and information were gathered for this study to meet its objectives and provide answers to the research questions. In the initial step in this process, the researchers coordinated with the managers or secretaries of the selected tourist attractions to set schedules and obtain permission to distribute the survey. Once the availability of respondents on the designated date was confirmed, the researchers distributed the survey questionnaires in person. This chosen approach is needed for the study as it is possible that the chosen respondents may not be familiar on how to use online survey platforms, so it is much better to go to the traditional way of data gathering. For them to better understand the purpose of the study, the researchers explained the methodology and goals of the study before disseminating the questionnaires to them so that confusions may be avoided. It is also explained that if they have questions regarding the questionnaire, they can ask them anytime along with the assurance that all the information they provided remained anonymous and not be shared with anyone not involved in the study.

This assurance aimed to encourage participants to provide honest and thoughtful responses. After data collection was completed, the researchers carefully organized and analyzed the responses. Through this systematic data gathering approach, the study aimed to generate meaningful insights to help tourist attractions in Tagaytay improve their disaster risk preparedness practices.

Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistical tools, including frequency, percentage, and mean, to summarize the responses. These methods were used to determine patterns in disaster risk awareness and preparedness practices. Data analysis was conducted using Microsoft Excel, and results were interpreted using standard descriptive ranges. No inferential statistical tests or significance levels were applied, as the study focused on descriptive analysis.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The study included five respondents from selected tourist attractions in Tagaytay City. In terms of age, the majority belonged to the 50–59 age group (40%), while the remaining respondents were evenly distributed across the 20–29, 30–39, and 40–49 age groups (20% each). No respondents were aged 60 and above.

With respect to gender, most respondents were female (80%), while males accounted for 20% of the sample. In terms of business type, respondents were primarily from museums (40%) and parks (40%), with one respondent from a theme park (20%). No participants represented hotels or restaurants. These findings indicate that the data were derived from a limited and specialized group of respondents, which may influence the generalizability of the results across the broader tourism sector.

Level of Disaster Risk Awareness

The results revealed a high level of disaster risk awareness among respondents, with a grand mean of 3.67. The highest-rated indicator was awareness of potential natural disaster risks affecting operations (Mean = 4.0 ± 0.0), followed by understanding of emergency procedures and evacuation protocols (Mean = 3.8 ± 0.4). Awareness of environmental monitoring and preventive measures also showed consistently high ratings (Mean = 3.6–3.8). However, preparedness in terms of emergency supplies received a comparatively lower score (Mean = 3.2 ± 0.4), indicating a gap between awareness and practical readiness. These findings suggest that while tourism establishments demonstrate strong knowledge of disaster risks, implementation of physical preparedness measures remains inconsistent. This supports previous studies emphasizing that awareness alone does not always translate into effective preparedness practices. The observed gap may be attributed to resource limitations and operational constraints, particularly among smaller establishments.

Indicator	Mean Score	Interpretation
Awareness of disaster risks	4.0	Highly Aware
Understanding of emergency procedures	3.8	Highly Aware
Training and preparedness seminars	3.6	Highly Aware
Familiarity with evacuation procedures	3.8	Highly Aware
Preparedness with emergency supplies	3.2	Aware
Environmental monitoring awareness	3.6	Highly Aware
Preventive infrastructure measures	3.6	Highly Aware
Grand Mean	3.67	Highly Aware

Legend: 1.00–1.74 (Not Aware); 1.75–2.49 (Slightly Aware); 2.50–3.24 (Aware); 3.25–4.00 (Highly Aware)

Table No. 1. Summary of Disaster Risk Awareness and Preparedness

Disaster Preparedness Measures

The implementation of disaster preparedness measures among respondents was also rated highly, with a grand mean of 3.67. The highest-rated practice was maintaining updated emergency contact information (Mean = 4.0 ± 0.0), followed by the presence of evacuation plans and clearly marked exits (Mean = 3.8 ± 0.4). Other measures, including availability of first aid kits, backup power supply, insurance coverage, and coordination with local government units, were also rated highly (Mean = 3.6–3.8). In contrast, the conduct of regular emergency drills received a lower mean score (Mean = 3.2 ± 0.4), indicating that while systems are in place, consistent practice and reinforcement may be lacking. These results align with prior research highlighting that tourism establishments often prioritize structural and procedural measures over continuous training and simulation exercises. The limited emphasis on drills may reduce the effectiveness of preparedness plans during actual disaster situations.

Indicator	Mean Score	Interpretation
Emergency evacuation plan	3.8	Highly Aware
Conduct of emergency drills	3.2	Aware
Clearly marked emergency exits	3.8	Highly Aware
Updated emergency contact list	4.0	Highly Aware
Availability of first aid supplies	3.6	Highly Aware
Backup power supply	3.6	Highly Aware
Insurance coverage	3.6	Highly Aware
Coordination with local authorities	3.8	Highly Aware
Grand Mean	3.67	Highly Aware

Table No. 2. Disaster Preparedness Measures Implemented

Challenges in Disaster Preparedness

The findings identified several challenges affecting disaster preparedness among tourism establishments. Key issues included limited financial resources, insufficient training opportunities, and the lack of regular updates to disaster management plans. These challenges suggest that despite high awareness levels, practical implementation is constrained by operational limitations. Similar findings have been reported in previous studies, where resource availability and institutional support significantly influence preparedness capacity. The small sample size and focus on specific types of

tourist attractions further limit the generalizability of these findings. However, the results highlight critical areas that require attention to improve disaster preparedness in the tourism sector.

Implications and Future Directions

The findings of this study contribute to a better understanding of disaster preparedness in tourism establishments within disaster-prone areas. The results support the need for stronger integration of awareness and practical implementation, particularly in terms of training, resource allocation, and continuous evaluation of preparedness strategies. From a practical perspective, the study suggests the need for enhanced collaboration between tourism establishments and local government units to develop standardized disaster preparedness programs. Policy interventions may include mandatory training, regular emergency drills, and financial support mechanisms to improve preparedness capacity. Future research may expand the sample size and include a wider range of tourism establishments, such as hotels and restaurants, to provide a more comprehensive analysis. Longitudinal studies may also be conducted to assess changes in preparedness over time and evaluate the effectiveness of implemented strategies.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the disaster risk preparedness of selected tourist attractions in Tagaytay City by assessing respondents' demographic profile, level of awareness, preparedness measures, and challenges encountered. The findings indicate that tourism establishments demonstrate a high level of disaster risk awareness and have implemented essential preparedness measures. However, gaps remain in areas such as emergency drills, resource allocation, and the regular updating of disaster management plans.

The study contributes to existing knowledge by reinforcing the idea that awareness alone is not sufficient to ensure effective disaster preparedness. While previous research emphasizes the importance of knowledge and planning, the findings highlight the need to bridge the gap between awareness and actual implementation, particularly in resource-constrained environments.

From a practical perspective, the results suggest the need for stronger collaboration between tourism establishments and local government units to enhance disaster preparedness efforts. Recommended actions include the implementation of regular emergency drills, provision of training programs, and development of standardized disaster preparedness guidelines tailored to different types of tourism establishments. These measures can improve operational resilience and ensure the safety of both tourists and employees.

The study acknowledges certain limitations, particularly the small sample size and the limited representation of tourism sectors, as respondents were drawn from only a few types of establishments. These limitations restrict the generalizability of the findings but also highlight opportunities for broader and more inclusive research in the future.

Future studies may expand the scope by including a larger and more diverse sample of tourism establishments, such as hotels and restaurants, and by applying inferential statistical methods to examine relationships between variables. Longitudinal research may also be conducted to assess changes in disaster preparedness over time and to evaluate the effectiveness of implemented interventions.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to all individuals and institutions who contributed to the completion of this study. Special thanks are extended to the Municipality of Tagaytay City for granting permission to conduct the research, as well as to the managers and staff of the selected tourist attractions for their participation and valuable insights.

The authors also acknowledge their research adviser, Ms. Reymarie A. Lobo, MBA, and Dr. Kristy Aireen Reamillo, for their guidance and support throughout the research process. Appreciation is likewise given to Ms. Kimberly Joy E. Alcaraz for her assistance in data analysis, and to the panel members for their constructive feedback.

Finally, the authors are grateful to their families and colleagues for their encouragement and support in completing this study.

Funding

This research received no external funding from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit funding agency, and no organization provided financial support for the conduct of the study, authorship, or publication of this article.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

References

- Balogun, A., Marks, D., Sharma, R., Shekhar, H., Balmes, C., Maheng, D., Arshad, A., & Salehi, P. (2019). Assessing the potentials of digitalization as a tool for climate change adaptation and sustainable development in urban centres. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 53, 101888. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2019.101888>
- Chan, C., Nozu, K., & Cheung, T. O. L. (2019). Tourism and natural disaster management process: perception of tourism stakeholders in the case of Kumamoto earthquake in Japan. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 23(15), 1864–1885. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2019.1666809>
- Guanzon, B. L., Aquino, P. J., Magallon, M., Romero, J. C., De Ocampo, L., Balila, J., Macalalad, M., Rivera, G. L., & Sausa, L. (2022). Exploring Business Resilience Amidst Volcanic Eruption and Pandemic: A Case Study in Food Establishments. *FIDERE: Journal of Business, Governance, & Information Technology*, 4(2). https://www.aup.edu.ph/urc/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/9-FIDERE-December-2022_compressed.pdf#page=64Balogun,%20A.%20L.
- Musawantoro, H. W. . D., . M. Z. B. . M. R. . M. (2022). Disaster Management for Tourism Destination in Labuan Bajo (Case Study on super Priority destinations). <https://www.webology.org/abstract.php?id=1442>
- Naeem, N., & Rana, I. A. (2020). Tourism and Disasters: A Systematic Review from 2010–2019. *Journal of Extreme Events*, 07(01n02), 2030001. <https://doi.org/10.1142/s234573762030001x>
- Shmueli, D. F., Ozawa, C. P., & Kaufman, S. (2020). Collaborative planning principles for disaster preparedness. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 52, 101981. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2020.101981>

Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.